

General Remarks

The instructions provided here are grounded in the Multilingual Assessment Instrument for Narratives (MAIN), developed as a component of the COST Action IS0804 “Language Impairment in a Multilingual Society: Linguistic Patterns and the Road to Assessment”. This initiative was part of the broader LITMUS (Language Impairment Testing in Multilingual Settings) framework (cf. Gagarina et al. 2019b). Comprehensive information regarding MAIN can be accessed on the official homepage at <https://main.leibniz-zas.de/>.

The materials and instructions were intended for testing with children of different ages and cultural backgrounds. These were developed, tested, and described by several members of the sizeable MAIN team (the persons involved are mentioned by name in the corresponding documents, e.g., Gagarina et al. 2019a). Following registration, all necessary materials for testing are made available, encompassing pictorial materials in various versions and instructions for testing with children. Using MAIN to assess picture-based narratives from children is widely established and has led to a broad corresponding research literature (see <https://main.leibniz-zas.de/en/research/publications/>).

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in utilizing the same material within the framework of adult testing (see Gagarina et al. 2019b; for a comprehensive overview, see Karl 2023). To ensure the collection of comparable data in adult contexts, it is essential to describe the test procedure that aligns with the principles and standards established for the childish context and adapt it to the corresponding adult context. The present documents are designed to serve this purpose by providing a detailed description of the test procedure.

Based on the comprehensive materials for testing with children, instructions are provided herein for adapting the testing of the same picture stories with adults. Logically, they strongly resemble the aforementioned instructions for testing with children. To ensure the highest possible comparability, linguistic care was taken to stay as close as possible to the MAIN documents. Consequently, the instructions provided here are partly congruent with those available for download on the MAIN homepage.

However, there are notable distinctions between the two sets of instructions. These pertain to the provision of the link through which the pictures are made available, the specific instructions given prior to the test, and an adapted version of the questions that can be posed after the narrative has been collected. These questions differ from those asked in the context of testing with children.

The adaptations were developed by Katrin B. Karl and her research team. They have already been successfully applied several times in the context of a research project on variations in narratives from Polish, Russian, and German-speaking adults. In the run-up to the study, several preliminary studies were conducted on the instructions. These included a comparison of remote testing with face-to-face testing and an evaluation of different remote testing versions. The latter comparison involved a link procedure, a shared-screen procedure, and an unmoderated procedure (cf. Karl 2023).

- The most salient points in the context of testing with adults are as follows (c.f. Karl 2023; further articles are currently being published):
- The utilization of MAIN for testing with adults has been demonstrated to be a beneficial approach, culminating in the elicitation of high-quality narratives that can be subject to meaningful analysis (see also Gagarina et al. 2019b).
- The efficacy of the tests is further demonstrated by their successful implementation in both face-to-face and remote settings, yielding favorable outcomes.
- The narratives elicited in person and via remote procedures are comparable for the age group of young adults (regarding the tested 20-25-year-old monolinguals).
- Among the remote methods, the so-called link method has proven to be the most suitable.

The instructions provided herein correspond to those utilized in my research project. A fundamental question of this project pertains to the impact of the change in the addressee when narrating picture-based stories. In alignment with this inquiry, the research design entails each adult participant narrating two MAIN stories, with the first story addressed to an adult and the second to an imagined child (c.f. Karl under review). They always refer to the telling mode.

In accordance with this design, the instructions include face-to-face testing and testing in a remote context (using the link version, which can be replaced by using the PPT and sharing the screen) with an adult addressee (1st story) and a child addressee (2nd story) in telling mode. These instructions are currently available in German, Russian, and Polish.

References:

- Gagarina, Natalia, Daleen Klop, Sari Kunnari, Koula Tantele, Taina Välimaa, Ute Bohnacker, and Joel Walters. 2019a. "MAIN: Multilingual assessment instrument for narratives–Revised." *ZAS Papers in Linguistics* 63: 20. <https://doi.org/10.21248/zaspil.63.2019.516>
- Gagarina, Natalia, Ute Bohnacker, and Josefin Lindgren. 2019b. "Macrostructural organization of adults' oral narrative texts." *ZAS Papers in Linguistics* 62: 190–208. <https://doi.org/10.21248/zaspil.62.2019.449>

Instructions for eliciting picture-based narratives from adults (using the Multilingual Assessment Instrument for Narratives – MAIN)

Katrin B. Karl, University of Bern

Karl, Katrin B. 2023. “Adapting MAIN to Eliciting Stories from Adults and in a Remote Context: What Do We Have to Consider, and What Do We Know?.” *ZAS Papers in Linguistics* 65 (März): 91-109. <https://doi.org/10.21248/zaspil.65.2023.622>

Karl, K.B. (under review). The influence of the addressee on picture-based narratives of adults: A comparative study.